

been screened, including internationally known cold-tolerant checks Stejaree 45, Akiyudaka, China 1039, Palung 2, Fuji 102, and Phalame.) Leaf color, panicle exsertion, spikelet sterility, and yield parameters were scored visually at seedling, booting, anthesis, and maturity stages.

Above 1,400 m, most of the exotic varieties either failed to produce panicles or produced degenerated spikelets with a high degree of sterility. Yield performance of indigenous cultivars was reliable above 1,300 m (Fig. 2). At 1,500 m altitude, local variety Chhomro outyielded all other varieties; at 2,000 m, its performance was outstanding. This variety demonstrated an ability to tolerate

chilling at different growth stages at all altitudes.

The National Variety Releasing Board has released Chhomro as Chhomrong dhan, the first indigenous variety for areas above 1,400 m asl. It also has been included as a cold-tolerant entry in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery and LRARC's chilling-tolerant rice breeding program. Results on segregating materials resulting from crosses between Chhomrong and exotic cold-tolerant lines are very promising.

Identification in recent years of Chhomrong dhan and several other varieties suitable for the low to high hills of Nepal has confirmed the value of field screening at different altitudes. □

Grain yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content

2. Yield of Chhomro and mean yields of NRCTN across altitudes, 1987-88.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Response of some rice cultivars to lime application on acid sulfate soils

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We studied the effect of lime on rice cultivar yields in acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, during the 1989 dry season (Table 1).

In split-plot design with three replications, four lime levels (0, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 t/ha) were the main plot treatments and five rice cultivars (BW267-3, CR261-

7039-236, IR6023-10-1-1, Kapuas, and IR26) were subplot treatments. Lime was applied 15 d before transplanting. Three 21-d-old seedlings/hill were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 5-m plots. At transplanting, we fertilized the rice basally with 90 kg N/ha, 26.4 kg P/ha, and 41.5 kg K/ha.

Table 2. Effect of lime on yield of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, 1989 dry season.

Lime (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	BW267-3	CR261-7039-236	IR6023-10-1-1	Kapuas	IR26
0	1.7	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.3
0.5	2.1	1.5	1.5	2.1	1.4
1.0	2.1	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.0
2.0	2.6	1.7	2.1	2.6	2.2
Mean	2.1	1.6	1.8	2.1	1.7

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of acid sulfate soil at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

	0-20 cm deep	20-40 cm deep
pH (H ₂ O)	3.95	3.90
Total N (%)	0.41	0.19
Organic C (%)	2.78	1.70
Available P (ppm)	17.63	32.96
Exchangeable K (meq/100g)	0.19	0.13
SO ₄ (%)	0.12	0.05
Al ³⁺ (meq/100g)	14.19	15.70
Na (meq/100 g)	0.12	0.26
Fe ³⁺ (meq/100 g)	6.16	5.59
Particle size (%)		
Sand	0.22	0.21
Silt	33.41	31.14
Clay	66.37	68.65

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

New rice cultivar Marianna obtained through anther culture

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Marianna is a new short-stemmed, lodging-resistant rice cultivar.

Yields in plots with 2.0 t lime/ha were significantly higher than those at other levels (Table 2).

In the cultivar treatments, Kapuas and BW267-3 yielded significantly higher than other varieties. In general, yield increased as lime was added. □

It is a dihaploid line, obtained from a 1983 F₁ hybrid combination Belozem/Plovdiv 22 through anther culture.

We tested Marianna alone and with other cultivars until 1986. From 1986 to 1989, it was tested in some regular trials at State Cultivar Commission stations. It was acknowledged as an original cultivar at the commission's 45th plenary session.

Marianna is related to the japonica rices. Its vegetative phase is 121-125 d,

Characteristics of Marianna compared with standard Krasnodarsky 424.

Indicator	Krasnodarsky 424	Marianna
Stem height (cm)	116.0	120.0
Preflag length (cm)	36.9	43.2
Preflag width (mm)	1.2	1.4
Central panicle length (cm)	19.8	21.0
Seeds (no.) in central panicle	104.4	131.7
1000-seed wt (g)	31.0	32.5
Av yield from a panicle (g)	2.1	2.4
Stem thickness (mm)	0.9	1.5
Yield (t/ha)	5.4	6.1

comparable to that of standard Krasnodarsky 424 (see table). It has tall, thick, nonlodging stems, and wide, erect, intensively pigmented leaves. Increased dynamics characterizes initial growth and development phases.

The egg-shaped grain is suitable for mechanized polishing and is highly resistant to breakage. □

Zhe 733, a high-yielding, blast (B1)-resistant, good quality indica rice for China

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In recent years, indica rice breeders have been incorporating multiple resistance into high-yielding varieties. We identified Zhe 733 as having good yield potential and B1 resistance rated 3 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Zhe 733 was a multiple cross of IR30, IR29, Fongxuan 4, and Chi-Kuai-Ai-Xuan, released in Mar 1991 as an early rice in the double-cropped Yangtze River area.

Zhe 733 had high, stable yield potential under normal fertilization. In regional trials in 1990, it yielded 6.4-7.8 t/ha (Table 1), 6-12% higher than the check Guangluai 4. Average growth duration was 112 d in Zhejiang, 2 d earlier than Guangluai 4. Approximately 55,000 ha is now planted to Zhe 733 in South China. Morphoagronomic characters are given in Table 2.

Table 1. B1 resistance and yield potentials of Zhe 733 in China, 1990.

Site	Yield (t/ha)		Resistance to B1 ^a	
	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7.8	6.9	3	7
Changsha, Hunan	7.8	6.8	3	9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	6.5	5.5	1	
Fuzhou, Fujian	6.4	6.1	3	9

^aBy SES.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characteristics of Zhe 733 at different sites in China, 1990.

Site	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	1,000-wt (g)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	113	81	19.8	89	72	19.1	25.8
Changsha, Hunan	111	83	20.4	98	80	18.4	26.9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	112	79	19.0	84	67	20.2	25.7
Fuzhou, Fujian	111	80	19.1	90	73	18.9	25.7

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, cooking and eating quality meet the China national index for high quality rice. Grain length is 6.8 mm, with a 2.8 length-breadth ratio. The grain is semitranslucent with 24.9% amylose,

10.3% protein content, low-gelatinization temperature (5.3 alkali spreading value), and medium gel consistency (60 mm). Hulling recovery is 81.9%; milling recovery, 74.1%; and head rice recovery, 52.6%. □

Response to nitrogen of new dwarf fragrant rice varieties for transplanted conditions

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Pusa Basmati 1 and Kasturi are new dwarf fragrant rice varieties released in India in 1990. Pusa Basmati 1, a semi-dwarf of medium duration (133-135 d), has a yield potential of 4 t/ha. Kasturi is semitall, of medium duration (130-135 d) with a yield potential over 4 t/ha. Both varieties have long, slender grains with strong aroma. Kasturi also has good kernel elongation. Both are suited to the irrigated ecosystem and have export potential.

We compared Pusa Basmati 1, Kasturi and another promising variety, HKR228, with local check Basmati 370 at 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha under optimum management. The soil was Aquic Hapludoll, silt loam, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N. The

Performance of newly released Basmati rice varieties at different N levels at Pantnagar, 1990 wet season.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha) at 14% moisture			
	N ₆₀	N ₉₀	N ₁₂₀	Mean
Pusa Basmati 1	2.8	3.1	3.2	3.0
Kasturi	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4
HKR228	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.3
Basmati 370 (local check)	2.2	2.8	2.8	2.6
Mean	2.8	3.2	3.3	
<u>Treatment</u>	<u>LSD (0.05)</u>			
Variety	0.2			
N rate	0.5			
Variety × N interaction	ns			

experiment was laid out in split-plot design, with four replications (N rate in main plots, and varieties in subplots).

Seedlings were raised in wet nurseries (20 Jun sowing) and transplanted on 20 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha as per normal practice. We applied urea in three splits: 1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, and 1/4 at 1 wk before panicle initiation.

The Basmati varieties showed no differential response to N. N response